

A CONCEPTUAL AND CLINICAL BRIDGE BETWEEN PCOD AS AARTVA DUSHTI

Dr. Jaya More*¹, Dr. Shilpa Desai², Dr. Pallavi Chandanshiv³

PG Scholar¹, Professor², Professor and HOD³

Yashwantrao Chavan Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar.

Article Received on 15 Nov. 2025,
Article Revised on 05 Dec. 2025,
Article Published on 15 Dec. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17949613>

*Corresponding Author

Dr. Jaya More

PG Scholar, Yashwantrao Chavan
Ayurvedic College and Hospital,
Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar.

How to cite this Article: Dr. Jaya More*¹, Dr. Shilpa Desai², Dr. Pallavi Chandanshiv³. (2025). A CONCEPTUAL AND CLINICAL BRIDGE BETWEEN PCOD AS AARTVA DUSHTI. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 14(24), 490-498.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) is a multifactorial endocrine disorder characterised primarily by chronic anovulation, along with clinical manifestations such as irregular menstrual periods, hirsutism, and weight gain. It is the most prevalent female endocrine disorder and a leading cause of infertility worldwide. The global prevalence of PCOS ranges between 6 to 26%, with Indian prevalence reported between 3.7 to 22.5%. Polycystic Ovarian Disease, often used interchangeably with PCOS, is marked by hyperandrogenism and polycystic ovarian morphology. Ayurveda classifies menstrual disorders under the broad category of *Aartavdushti*, which includes abnormalities in menstrual flow, duration, colour, consistency, and associated symptoms. The findings demonstrate that PCOD corresponds clinically to several forms of *Aartavdushti*, mainly *Artavakshaya*, *Yoni Vedana*, *Yonivritta*

Artava, *Granthi-yukta Artava* (presence of cystic formations). The pathogenesis of PCOD is interpreted as a consequence of *Kapha-Vata dosha* predominance, *Agnidushti*, and *Avarana*, resulting in menstrual irregularities categorised under *Aartavdushti*. Ayurvedic interventions such as *Agnideepana*, *Amapachana*, *Lekhana*, *Vatanulomana*, and *Shodhana* present promising integrative management strategies. This synthesis of Ayurvedic and modern perspectives for the treatment of PCOD and related menstrual dysfunctions.

KEYWORDS: PCOD, *Aartavdushti*, *Shodhana*, Menstrual disorders, *Artavkshaya*.

INTRODUCTION

Polycystic Ovarian Disease (PCOD), often used interchangeably with Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS), is one of the most common endocrine and metabolic disorders affecting women of reproductive age, with global prevalence estimates ranging from 6% to 13%^[1], and Indian prevalence reported between 3.7% to 22.5%.^[2] A complex interplay of reproductive, metabolic, and psychological disturbances, including anovulation, hyperandrogenism, polycystic ovarian morphology, insulin resistance, obesity, irregular menstrual cycles, acne, hirsutism, weight gain, and infertility, characterises it. With rising stress levels, sedentary lifestyle patterns, and dietary imbalances, the burden of PCOD has increased significantly, making it a major health concern that adversely affects women's quality of life and long-term health outcomes.

In Ayurveda, female reproductive health is fundamentally governed by *Aartav*, described as the essential factor for menstruation and conception. *Acharya Charaka* states, “**Aartavam nāma strīṇām garbhasya hetuḥ**” - *Aartav* is the cause of conception in women.^[3] *Acharya Sushrut* further describes normal menstruation as having proper colour, quantity, and duration.^[4] Any deviation in the attributes of *Aartav* due to *Doṣhadushti* results in *Aartavdushti*, which includes abnormalities in colour, consistency, odour, quantity, and timing of menstrual flow.

Aṣṭanga Samgraha and *Aṣṭanga Hṛidaya* describe various types of *Aartavdushti*—*Vataj*, *Pittaj*, *Kaphaj*, and *Tridoṣhaj*—each characterised by specific disturbances in menstrual patterns. *Vatadushti* leads to delayed or scanty menstruation and anovulation. *Pittadushti* causes excessive, painful, or discoloured bleeding. *Kaphadushti* results in heavy, sticky, and sluggish menstrual flow.^[5] These descriptions show remarkable conceptual overlap with the clinical manifestations of PCOD. *Kapha*-dominance corresponds to cyst formation, obesity, and metabolic sluggishness; *Vata* aggravation aligns with anovulation and irregular cycles; and *Pitta* disturbance parallels hormonal imbalance and inflammatory changes. Thus, PCOD can be interpreted as a multifactorial condition rooted in *Doshadushti* leading to multiple forms of *Aartav Dushti*, including conditions such as *Anartava* and *Pushpaghni Yonivyapada*.

Ayurveda also identifies etiological factors relevant to PCOD under *Mithya ahara-vihara*—improper diet, sedentary habits, excessive sleep, emotional stress, and incompatible food combinations.^[6] These factors are closely aligned with modern etiological concepts that contribute to hormonal imbalance.

Ayurvedic management emphasises restoring *Doṣha* balance, improving *Agni* and metabolism, regulating *Aartav*, and rejuvenating reproductive tissues through herbal formulations, *Panchakarma* procedures, Rasayana therapy, and diet-lifestyle modifications. Medicinal preparations such as *Kumariasava*, *Ashokariṣṭa*, *Rajahpravartini Vati*, *Chāṇḍraprabha Vati*, and *Shatapushpa Churṇa* are used to correct *Aartav Dushti* and support ovarian function.

This integrated viewpoint helps bridge Ayurvedic insights with modern medical insights. The present article aims to explore the conceptual correlation between PCOD and *Aartav Dushti*, analyse their shared pathophysiological basis, examine clinical presentations, and outline therapeutic approaches for effective management.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

- Synthesise current understanding of PCOS from both modern and Ayurvedic perspectives
- Examine the conceptual mapping between PCOS and *Aartavdushti*
- Evaluate evidence for ayurvedic treatment approaches

METHODOLOGY

Classical Ayurvedic texts, including *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushrut Samhita*, *Aṣṭāṅg Hṛidaya*, and relevant commentaries, were reviewed. Chapters dealing with *Yonivyapada*, *Artava Vikara*, *Dosha-Dushya Samurcchana*, and *Avarana* were analysed. Modern medical textbooks, databases and clinical guidelines on PCOD were reviewed to identify symptom patterns, diagnostic criteria, and pathophysiological mechanisms.

PCOS

Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) is described as a heterogeneous endocrine disorder characterised by chronic anovulation and hyperandrogenism, often associated with polycystic ovarian morphology on ultrasound⁷. It is considered one of the most common causes of menstrual irregularities, subfertility, and metabolic disturbances in women of reproductive age.

PCOS is a complex, multifactorial disorder involving^[8]

- **Endocrine Dysfunction**
 1. Hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian axis dysregulation
 2. Hyperandrogenism

3. Anovulation: Arrested follicular development due to hormonal imbalances

- **Metabolic Dysfunction**

1. Insulin resistance: Present in 50-70% of PCOS patients, independent of obesity
2. Compensatory hyperinsulinemia: Stimulates ovarian androgen production
3. Adipose tissue dysfunction: Altered adipokine secretion contributing to metabolic and reproductive abnormalities
4. Dyslipidaemia: Increased cardiovascular risk profile

- **Genetic and Environmental Factors**

1. Familial clustering
2. Epigenetic modifications influenced by the intrauterine environment
3. Lifestyle factors (diet, physical activity)

Clinical features

1. Menstrual irregularities – Oligomenorrhea, Amenorrhea, Dysfunctional uterine bleeding
2. Hyperandrogenic signs – Hirsutism, Acne, Alopecia
3. Reproductive problems – Chronic anovulation, Infertility/ Subfertility
4. Metabolic problems – Obesity, Insulin resistance, Dyslipidaemia, risk of type 2 diabetes
5. USG features – enlarged ovaries, peripheral arrangement of multiple small follicles (string of pearls appearance), increased stromal echogenicity

Diagnostic Criteria in Modern Medicine

- **Rotterdam Criteria (2003)^[9]**: 2 out of 3 features required

1. Oligo- or anovulation
2. Clinical and/or biochemical hyperandrogenism
3. Polycystic ovaries on ultrasound

- **NIH Criteria (1990)^[10]**: Both features required

1. Hyperandrogenism (clinical or biochemical)
2. Oligo- or anovulation

Management of PCOS

Management includes lifestyle modifications, such as diet, exercise, weight reduction activities etc. Along with these in modern treatment, hormonal therapy, as oc pills, antiandrogens were used.

ARTAVDUSHTI

In Ayurveda, *Aartavdushti* (*Artava-vaha srotodusthi*) is characterised as:

- Impairment of the *Agani*
- Involvement of *Vata* and *Kapha* doshas
- *Dhatudushti*, particularly *Rasa*, *Rakta*, *Meda*, *Shukra*
- Obstruction or dysfunction in *Artava-vaha strotas*

The concept encompasses not merely menstrual irregularity but a systemic imbalance affecting multiple physiological systems.

Clinical features of *Aartavdushti* as

- *Pushpaghani* (destruction of menstrual flow)
- *Artavakshaya* (diminution of menstrual blood)

Nidanpanchaka of *Aartavdushti*^[11]

1) *Nidana*

- *Mithya Ahara*: Excessive intake of *Kapha*-aggravating foods, irregular eating patterns
- *Mithya Vihara*: Sedentary lifestyle, lack of physical activity, daytime sleeping
- *Manasika*: Stress, anxiety, emotional disturbances
- *Pradushtarthava dusthi*: the irregularities of the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian axis
- *Beeja dushti*: Various chromosomal and genetic abnormalities

2) *Samprapti*

Due to *Mithya aahara- vihara Kapha* get vitiated, furtherly it impaires the function of *Agni*, resulting *Agnimandya* & leads to formation of *Ama*.

Without the aggravation of *Vata*, the women's *Yoni* does not get vitiated. As we know, *Vata* is responsible for all the activities of *Pitta* & *Kapha*.

Here, *Vata*, specifically *Apana vayu*, governs the downward expulsion of *Shukra*, *Aartav*, *Mala*, *Mutra*, *Garbha*. Vitiated *Kapha* obstructs the normal functioning of *Apana Vayu*, these

further hampers the movement of *Pitta*, ultimately disturbs the physiological flow and hormonal regulation.

Accumulation of *Kapha* and *Ama* causes *strotorodha*. The combined vitiation of *Vata* and *Kapha* produces *Avaraṇa* in *Aartavvaha Srotas*, ultimately resulting in *Aartavnasha*.

Samprapti Ghatak

1. *Dosha: Kapha, Vata*
2. *Dushya: Medo, Rasa, Rakta*
3. *Srotas: Artavvaha, Medovaha*
4. *Strotodusti: Sangha*
5. *Agni: Manda*

3) ***Poorvarupa***: Slight irregularities in menstrual cycle, weight gain, acne, etc.

4) *Roopa*

1. Menstrual irregularities such as oligomenorrhea, amenorrhea included in various *Yonirogas* (*Vandhya, Pushpaghni, Jataharini*) and *Arthava Vyapaths* (*Arthavakshaya, Nashtarthava, Asrigdara*)
2. Obesity, described as *Sthoulya*^[12]
3. Hyperandrogenic symptoms such as acne and baldness can be correlated with *Yuvaan pitika* and *Khalitya* respectively.
4. Hirsutism is described as *Athilomatha*
5. Hyperinsulinaemia, described under *Prameha*.

5) ***Sadhya-asadhyata***: *Kricchra-sadhya vyadhi* or *Yapya vyadhi*.

6) ***Chikitsa***: *Kaphaghna, Srotoshodhaka, Deepana-Pachana, Vatashamak, Medohara chikitsa* should be given as *shaman chikitsa* in *Aartavdushti/PCOS*.

Some medicines like, *Shatavari, Ashoka, Lodhra, Guduchi, Haritaki, Guggulu*, etc. and some preparations like *Triphala guggulu, Kanchanar guggulu, Pushpadhanva rasa, Kunariasava, Dashmoolarishta*, etc. were used.

These medicines have anti-inflammatory, antioxidant properties, direct action on reproductive tissues, hormone modulation, etc.

In *Shodhana chikitsa*, such as *Basti (Matra, Niruha, Uttarbasti)*, *Vamana*, *Virechana* should be given and these shows very successful results in cases of PCOS/ *Aartavdushti*.

7) *Pathya- Apathya*

- *Pathyakar aahar: Laghu, Ushna, Ruksha, Kaphaghna aahar*
- *Pathyakar Vihar: Vyayam, Yoga, Active lifestyle*
- *Apathyakar aahar: Guru, Snigdha, Madhura, Sheeta, Kapha vardhak aahar*
- *Apathyakar vihar: Diwaswap, Aalasya, Sedentary lifestyle*

Asana for PCOS^[13]

1. *Malasana*
2. *Adhomukhshwanasana*
3. *Bhujangasan*
4. *Baddhakonasana*
5. *Janushirsana*
6. *Ushtrasana*
7. *Surya namaskar*

DISCUSSION

The pathophysiology of PCOD closely parallels the Ayurvedic concept of *Artava Kshaya*, characterized by *Kapha–Meda* accumulation, *Strotorodha*, and vitiation of *Apana Vata*. Ayurveda offers a multidimensional treatment framework that addresses metabolic disturbances, hormonal imbalance, and reproductive dysfunction. Panchakarma procedures—such as *Vamana*, *Virechana*, and *Basti*—aim to remove the underlying causative factors, while *Shamana* therapies help restore normal ovarian and menstrual physiology.

This holistic approach not only regulates menstrual cycles but also improves ovulation, fertility potential, and overall metabolic health—areas where conventional therapy often remains primarily symptomatic. The association of PCOD with *Artavakshaya* highlights Ayurveda's integrative potential in managing this multifaceted disorder. The Ayurvedic explanation of pathogenesis aligns well with biomedical insights regarding hormonal dysregulation, metabolic syndrome, and ovarian changes. By focusing on *dosha* balance and *Agni* optimization, Ayurvedic interventions provide a comprehensive strategy that addresses both systemic and localized aspects of PCOD. Nonetheless, further well-designed clinical

studies are needed to substantiate these integrative approaches and enhance treatment outcomes.

Key parallels between *Aartavdushti* and PCOS include

- Recognition of the *Bahudoshaja* nature of the condition
- Understanding of both **metabolic and reproductive** components
- Emphasis on **lifestyle modifications** in disease development and management

CORRELATION

- *Srotorodha* parallels follicular arrest.
- *Kapha-Meda Vriddhi* resembles metabolic syndrome and insulin resistance.
- *Vata Dushti* correlates with menstrual irregularities.
- *Artava Kṣhaya* corresponds with oligomenorrhea and scanty menstruation in PCOD.

CONCLUSION

PCOS is a multisystem disorder involving reproductive, endocrine, and metabolic dysfunctions. Chronic anovulation, hyperandrogenism, and metabolic derangements form the triad of the condition.

PCOD, though defined in modern terms, can be comprehensively interpreted through the Ayurvedic lens as a condition arising from *Kapha-Vata* vitiation and *Artavadushti*. Integrating Ayurvedic therapies with lifestyle modifications offers a highly effective, individualised, and holistic strategy for managing PCOD and its reproductive complications. The approach emphasises the long-term correction of metabolic and hormonal imbalances, promoting sustained reproductive health and wellness.

REFERENCES

1. https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/polycystic-ovary-syndrome#:~:text=PCOS%20is%20a%20common%20hormonal%20condition%20that,medicines%20*%20Surgery%20to%20stimulate%20regular%20ovulation
2. <https://actascientific.com/ASWH/pdf/ASWH-04-0332.pdf>
3. Charaka Samhita, elaborated Vidyotini Hindi Commentary by Pt. Kashinath Shastri and Dr. Gorakha Nath Chaturvedi, Part-2 Chaukhamba Bharti Academy, Varanasi, 2020; Sharirasthana 2/4.

4. Sushrut Samhita of Maharshi Sushruta edited with Ayurveda tattva Sandipika, Hindi commentary, by Kaviraja Ambikadutta Shastri, Part I, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanasi, Sharirasthan 10/3.
5. Ashtang hridayam of Shrivagbhata edited with Nirmala hindi commentary by Dr. Bramhanand Tripathi, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan, Delhi, Sharirasthan 1/9–12.
6. Charaka Samhita, elaborated Vidyotini Hindi Commentary by Pt. Kashinath Shastri and Dr. Gorakha Nath Chaturvedi, Part-2 Chaukhamba Bharti Academy, Varanasi, 2020; Sutrasthan 28/7–8.
7. DC Dutta's Textbook of Gynecology, edited by Hiralal Konar.
8. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC9964744/>
9. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8409808/>
10. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7860982/#:~:text=Stein%20and%20Leventhal%20are%20generally,using%20the%20NIH%20criteria%2019>
11. Ayurvediya Prasuti Tantra Evum Striroga, Part II, Striroga (Gynaecology) by Prof. Premvati Tewari, Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, chapter 2.
12. Sharma R K, Bhagawan Dash. Charaka Samhita Sutra sthana. Varanasi: Chaukamba Sanskrit series, 2013; 374.
13. BijendarSingh, Jyoti Badola and Vijay Laxmi. The Positive effects of Asanas and Pranayama on PCOS and How to deal with a hormonal imbalance? International Journal for Modern Trends in Science and Technology, 2021; 7, 0707029: 190-195.